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ANALYSIS OF ENERGY INTENSITY AND FACTORS AFFECTING IT IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: Energy efficiency and energy intensity are the basis of today's economic and social significance. The terms energy efficiency and energy intensity are used to assess the use of energy resources, but differ in their meanings, methodology, and application. This article analyzes the importance of energy efficiency (ES) and energy intensity (EI) in industrial enterprises and the factors affecting them, fixed capital investments (AKI), the volume of product production in industrial enterprises (SMX), the volume of energy consumption in industrial enterprises (EX), and the volume of production of renewable energy sources (QTE) using econometric statistics, and presents forecast values of energy intensity for the future period.

Key words: Energy intensity, energy efficiency, fixed capital investment, industrial enterprises, energy consumption, Holt-Winters nonseasonal smoothing model.

INTRODUCTION

Energy intensity refers to the amount of energy consumed per unit of economic activity (e.g., gross domestic product, industrial production, goods, and services). In today's world, it is crucial for every country focusing on economic development to consider energy intensity. This metric reflects the economic efficiency of energy resource utilization and indicates the extent to which a state or society depends on energy in a particular sector.

The formula for calculating energy intensity is as follows:

$$EI = (ES)/IK$$

Where:

EI = Energy intensity index;

ES = Total energy consumption (measured in GJ, kWh, or tonnes of oil equivalent);

IK = Economic indicator (e.g., GDP, industrial output, or gross domestic product).

As shown in the formula, energy intensity is significant not only for industrial economic indicators but also for macroeconomic assessments.

The importance of energy intensity in industrial enterprises lies in its ability to provide insights into energy efficiency and economic performance. These aspects help determine whether an enterprise has a **positive** or **negative** energy intensity, influencing overall industrial sustainability.

Figure 1. Key aspects of energy intensity in industrial enterprises¹ [1].

Based on the above, we can observe an inverse relationship between energy intensity and energy efficiency. Energy intensity serves as the primary method for assessing how efficiently a country or sector utilizes its energy resources. Understanding this metric allows for more effective energy policy planning, investment strategies, and innovation development.

For Uzbekistan, reducing energy intensity is crucial for ensuring energy security and economic stability in the current era.

When examining developed countries, we notice that their energy intensity indicators are relatively low, which suggests that these nations utilize energy as efficiently as possible.

Below is a table presenting the countries with the highest and lowest energy intensity, based on data from 2022-2023.

Table 1. The 5 countries with the highest energy intensity [2].

Country	Energy intensity indicator (MG/\$, GDP)	Main reasons
Ukraine	15.2	Heavy industry, outdated infrastructure, dependence on coal
Russia	12.5	Oil and gas extraction industry, low energy efficiency
South Africa	11.8	Coal-fired electricity generation, heavy industry
Kazakhstan	10.9	Oil and metallurgical industry, cold climate
Saudi Arabia	10.5	Oil-dependent economy, energy subsidies

As seen in the table above, the primary reasons for high energy intensity in these countries include outdated infrastructure, reliance on heavy industry, and dependence on oil and coal as the main sources of energy production.

Among these nations, Ukraine and Russia rank at the top in terms of high energy intensity. This is mainly due to their specialization in heavy industry, which requires significant energy consumption.

The table below presents the five countries with the lowest energy intensity.

¹ Source: Developed by the author based on research

Table 2. The 5 countries with the lowest energy intensity [3].

Country	Energy intensity indicator (MG/\$, GDP)	Main reasons
Switzerland	2.3	High technologies, service sector, energy-saving policy
Denmark	2.5	Transition to renewable energy (40% wind energy), energy standards
Ireland	2.7	IT and pharmaceutical industries, energy efficiency programs
England	3.1	Decline of heavy industry, "Green energy" projects
Singapore	3.2	Smart city infrastructure, energy management systems

Attracting investments in high-tech and renewable energy to reduce energy intensity has become a priority for developed countries such as Switzerland and Denmark. Uzbekistan's energy intensity remains high due to its heavy industrial structure, dependence on fossil fuels, and limited technological modernization. Current estimates place Uzbekistan's energy intensity in the range of 6.5–8.5 MJ per USD of GDP. To address this issue, the government is accelerating the implementation of renewable energy projects, energy efficiency programs, and industrial modernization initiatives.

Based on the above, a number of targeted measures are being implemented to reduce energy intensity and improve energy efficiency in Uzbekistan.

In particular, several initiatives are being carried out under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. These initiatives include targeted plans and programs aimed at enhancing public well-being, increasing industrial production, addressing climate change, and fostering economic development. Notably, the declaration of 2025 as the "Year of Environmental Protection and Green Economy" by President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev further highlights the importance of this sector.

Additionally, according to Presidential Decree No. PF-16, issued on January 30, 2025, on "The state program for the implementation of the Uzbekistan-2030 strategy in the year of environmental protection and green economy"², a key priority is increasing the share of renewable energy in electricity generation. The decree outlines the following targets:

Increasing the share of renewable energy sources in total electricity generation to 26%

Raising the share of renewable energy in total generation capacity to 50%

Launching large-scale solar and wind power plants with a combined capacity of 4.5 GW

Installing solar panels with a capacity of 785 MW

Constructing hydroelectric power plants with a total capacity of 225 MW

These efforts demonstrate that, like many other nations, Uzbekistan is prioritizing its energy sector as a key driver of national development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Energy intensity is a key indicator that expresses the amount of energy consumed per unit of output in industrial enterprises. It plays an important role in assessing the energy efficiency, economic sustainability, and environmental impact of enterprises. In recent years, this topic has gained global importance due to the depletion of energy resources and climate change. Since energy intensity is a relatively complex concept, there has been little scientific research in this area to date. However, in their study on energy intensity, Allcott and Greenstone [6] identified the economic benefits of energy efficiency programs for households and enterprises, showing that their energy consumption can be reduced by **20–30%**. Jaffe and Stavins [7] also introduced the concept of the "**Energy Efficiency Gap**" into science and analyzed the barriers to the introduction of energy efficiency technologies (such as financial constraints, lack of information, etc.), highlighting their importance in energy intensity.

Technological innovations play a key role in reducing energy intensity in industrial enterprises. Hasanbeigi et al. [8] have shown in their research that energy consumption can be reduced by **20–40%** by introducing energy-efficient technologies (EST). For example, measures such as replacing electric motors with more efficient models or automating production processes are effective.

Energy management systems (EMS) are important in controlling energy intensity. Thollander et al. [9] found that energy consumption can be reduced by **15%** by implementing energy monitoring and auditing systems in enterprises.

In its "**Green Economy**" concept adopted in **2020** [10], Uzbekistan set a goal of reducing energy intensity

² <https://www.lex.uz/en/docs/7375421>

in industrial enterprises by **25% by 2030**. According to international experience (for example, the **EU Energy Efficiency Directive**), subsidies and tax incentives are the main investment flows aimed at encouraging enterprises to introduce energy-saving technologies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article analyzes the importance of energy efficiency (**EE**) and energy intensity (**EI**) in industrial enterprises and the factors affecting them, such as fixed capital investments (**FCI**), product production volume (**PPV**) in industrial enterprises, energy consumption volume (**ECV**) in industrial enterprises, and the production volume of renewable energy sources (**PRES**) using econometric statistics. Additionally, it presents forecast values of energy intensity for the future period.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In assessing energy intensity in industrial enterprises, it is essential to consider various influencing factors. By adjusting the impact of these factors, we can reduce energy intensity across the industrial sectors in our country and enhance overall energy efficiency. The selected factors and corresponding energy intensity indicators are presented in the table below.

Table 3. Energy intensity indicators in industry and factors influencing them³ [11].

Y	EU	AKI	EX	SMX	QTE
2010	1.363527	16463.7	51976.3	38119	8000
2011	1.109675	19500	52806.2	47587.1	6000
2012	0.920891	24455.3	52999.6	57552.5	7000
2013	0.773253	30490.1	54618.6	70634.8	7000
2014	0.663789	37646.2	55766	84011.6	6000
2015	0.59077	44810.4	57658.1	97598.2	7000
2016	0.528299	51232	59100.5	111869.4	7000
2017	0.408693	72155.2	60820.1	148816	8000
2018	0.267258	124231.3	62896.6	235340.7	6000
2019	0.196975	195927.3	63531.6	322535.8	6000
2020	0.180346	210195.1	66500.7	368740.2	5000
2021	0.156482	239552.6	71364.6	456056.1	5000
2022	0.134238	266240	74269.3	553265	5000
2023	0.118371	356071.4	78005.4	658991.7	7000

This table presents the energy intensity indicators (EI) in the industry and the factors affecting it (AKI, EX, SMX) by year.

Energy Intensity (EI): The energy intensity index has been continuously decreasing over the years. For example, EI, which was 1.363527 in 2010, declined to 0.118371 in 2023. This indicates that energy efficiency in the industrial sector has improved, leading to better energy utilization.

AKI (Fixed Capital Investment): The AKI indicator has increased significantly over the years. In 2010, AKI was 16,463.7, but by 2023, it had risen to 356,071.4. This suggests a significant rise in capital investment in the industrial sector, likely due to the implementation of new technologies and infrastructure improvements.

EX (Energy Volume): The energy volume indicator also exhibits an increasing trend. In 2010, exports stood at 51,976.3, rising to 78,005.4 in 2023. This suggests that the country's energy volume potential has increased, making it more competitive in foreign markets.

SMX (Industrial Output Volume): The SMX indicator shows a consistent upward trend. It increased from 38,119 in 2010 to 658,991.7 in 2023, indicating a significant rise in industrial product exports.

The decline in energy intensity and the simultaneous increase in other indicators suggest improvements in energy efficiency, investment levels, and export potential in the industrial sector. These trends reflect the development and stability of the economy.

³ Source: Developed by the author based on research

As a result of the research, we selected **AKI** and **QTE** as key influencing factors (**X1 and X2**) that contribute to changes in energy intensity in industrial enterprises. We conducted a statistical analysis to determine the significance and reliability of these factors using the **SATA programming language**.

The figure below illustrates the relationship between energy intensity, fixed capital investment, and renewable energy sources.

Figure 2. Graph of the relationship between EI, QTE and AKI.

The main purpose of taking the logarithm of the factors and the resulting signs here is to bring them to a uniform unit of measurement, since the units of measurement are different.

As can be seen from the figure above, there is a positive relationship between energy intensity and renewable energy, but an inverse relationship between energy intensity and fixed capital investment.

First, we will try to analyze the relationship between renewable energy and energy intensity through linear regression.

Table 4. Linear regression table between EI and QTE [12].

InEI	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	SSig
InQTE	3.633	1.39	2.61	.023	.605	6.661	**
Constant	-33.904	12.171	-2.79	.016	-60.423	-7.385	**
Mean dependent variable	-2.089		SD dependent var	0.973			
R-squared	0.363		Number of observations	14			
F-test	6.835		Probe > F	0.023			
Akaike crit. (AIC)	35,620		Bayesian crit. (BIC)	36,898			
*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1							

This data shows the results of the statistical analysis. The main aspects of the analysis are summarized and analyzed below.

InEI: This is the outcome (dependent variable) in the regression model, whose value is being analyzed through other variables (lnQTE).

InQTE: This is an independent variable with a coefficient of 3.633. This means that a one-unit change in lnQTE will change lnEI by 3.633 units. The t-value is 2.61, and the p-value is 0.023, indicating that lnQTE is statistically significant over lnEI ($p < 0.05$).

Constant: This is a constant term in the regression model, and its value is -33.904. This represents the expected value of lnEI when lnQTE is 0.

Sig: The double asterisk (**) symbol for lnQTE indicates its significance ($p < 0.05$).

R-squared: 0.363, which indicates the explanatory power of the model.

That is, 36.3% of the variation in lnEI is explained by lnQTE.

F-test: 6.835, indicating the overall significance of the model. Prob > F is 0.023, indicating that the model is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

In general, lnQTE is statistically superior to lnEI, and the model is generally significant. However, the R-squared value is relatively low, and adding other variables to the model may help to provide a better analysis. From the above, we can write the linear regression equation as follows:

$$\text{LnEI} = -33.904 + \text{lnQTE} * 3.633$$

We conduct a regression analysis on the importance of fixed capital investments on energy intensity, which we have selected as another influencing factor.

Table 5. Linear regression table between EI and AKI [13].

lnEI	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	SSig
lnAKI	-.912	.022	-40.98	0	-.961	-.864	***
Constant	8.151	.251	32.49	0	7.604	8.698	***
Mean dependent variable	-2.089		SD dependent var	0.973			
R-squared	0.993		Number of observations	14			
F-test	1679.351		Probe > F	0.000			
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-27.346		Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-26.068			
*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1							

This data shows the results of the regression analysis. The main points of the analysis are presented below.

lnEI: This is the outcome (dependent variable) in the regression model, whose value is being analyzed through other variables (lnAKI).

lnAKI: This is an independent variable with a coefficient of -0.912. This means that a one-unit change in lnAKI reduces lnEI by -0.912 units. The t-value is -40.98, and the p-value is 0, indicating that lnAKI is statistically superior to lnEI ($p < 0.01$).

Constant: This is a constant term in the regression model, and its value is 8.151. This represents the expected value of lnEI when lnAKI is 0.

Sig: The three asterisks (***) for lnAKI indicate its high significance ($p < 0.01$).

R-squared: 0.993, which indicates the explanatory power of the model. That is, 99.3% of the variation in lnEI is explained by lnAKI. This is a very high figure, indicating a good fit of the model.

F-test: 1679.351, indicating the overall significance of the model. Prob > F is 0.000, indicating that the model is statistically highly significant ($p < 0.01$).

$$\text{LnEI} = 8.151 - 0.912 * \text{lnAKI}$$

In general, the lnAKI-lnEI relationship shows very high statistical significance, and the model itself is highly significant. The R-squared value is exceptionally high, confirming a strong fit of the model. These results indicate that lnAKI plays a crucial role in analyzing lnEI. From the above, we can write the linear regression equation as follows.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, if energy is considered a top priority for the country, then economic development becomes essential for progress in all sectors. Energy intensity and efficiency play a crucial role in achieving this goal. Based on our research, we have identified the following key conclusions and proposals. The adoption of advanced technologies to enhance energy efficiency in industrial enterprises should be prioritized, along with the expansion of government grants and subsidies to support innovative projects.

Efficient resource management systems must be implemented within enterprises, and training programs

should be organized to enhance employees' skills. Regular energy audits should be conducted at enterprises, and modern systems for real-time energy consumption monitoring need to be introduced.

The government should develop national programs aimed at improving energy efficiency while also launching awareness campaigns to educate the public on the importance of energy conservation. A broader database should be utilized for analyzing energy intensity, and studies should take into account additional influencing factors such as energy prices and climate conditions. Reducing energy intensity is not only crucial for enhancing economic efficiency but also for ensuring environmental sustainability. Measures to improve energy efficiency should be comprehensive and integrated, covering technological, organizational, and administrative aspects. Effective long-term strategies for energy efficiency require close collaboration among the government, private sector, and academic institutions to ensure successful implementation. By applying these proposals, energy resources can be utilized more efficiently, leading to reduced energy intensity in the industrial sector, ultimately contributing to both economic growth and environmental sustainability.

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